

THE EFFICIENCY OF IMPROVING THE SOFTWARE OF TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF "NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES" IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the concept of network technologies, didactic software, method and methodology, "Case" method and other concepts were discussed.*

Keywords: *network technologies, pedagogical software tools, method, methodology, educational methods, FSMU, case study.*

In recent years, in our republic, further improving the education system, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market, introducing international standards for evaluating the quality of education and training, improving the quality and efficiency of the activities of higher education institutions are being created by effectively using innovative forms and methods of teaching, the latest pedagogical and information and communication technologies, distance learning and software, didactic supplies, normative foundations of teaching. "Automation of educational management using modern information and communication technologies in the educational process, creation of a single electronic platform for distance learning using modern educational technologies and new mechanisms for evaluating the skills of employees and using it for all educational purposes, introduction of highly effective international practices aimed at organizing training in the field of innovative activity into the educational system" are defined as priority tasks [1]. In this regard, the possibility of creating teaching-methodical materials and improving software for teaching natural and exact sciences in higher education institutions will expand.

In our republic, the use of network technologies in the organization of modern education in teaching subjects in higher education institutions, the use of innovative educational methods in classes, the increase of the intellectual potential of society based on new approaches, and the introduction of information technologies in the field of education have been created.

The purpose of teaching "Network technologies" in higher education institutions is to train mature personnel in the future through media management technology, network technologies, as a conceptual direction of the future teachers of informatics. At the current stage of education development, its main system-forming function is to create favorable conditions for training and educating a competitive, independent, active person [2]. The pedagogical essence of improving the software for teaching "Network technologies" is reflected as follows:

- eliminating the mandatory discreteness of the educational process, ensuring its continuity;
- the ability to take an independent direction in the accelerating flow of information, to make decisions, to ensure flexibility;
- including the student as a subject in the educational process, providing a whole, harmonized effect on a person.

Improving the higher education system with the latest modern information technologies and material technical base is one of the most important tasks of the state education policy. The

process of changing (updating) the continuous education system and its elements is one of the things that are carried out continuously. Therefore, education, as a social institution, must fully meet the modern requirements of the society and the country.

The impact of the current virtual world has both positive and negative aspects on the entire society. Pedagogical software tools can also be used in teaching "Network technologies".

Pedagogical software tools – is a didactic tool designed for partial or complete automation of the educational process with the help of computer technologies. They are considered one of the promising forms of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and are used as teaching tools of modern technologies. Pedagogical software tools include: a software product (set of programs) aimed at achieving specific didactic goals in a subject, technical and methodical support, additional auxiliary tools.

Pedagogical software tools can be divided into:

- educational programs - guide students to learn new knowledge based on their level of knowledge and interests;

- test programs - used for checking or evaluating acquired knowledge, skills and abilities;

- training programs serve to repeat and strengthen previously learned educational material;

- programs that create a virtual learning environment with the participation of the teacher.

Requirements for creating pedagogical software tools. In order to implement the technology of creating pedagogical software tools, there are a number of positive factors that confirm their superiority over traditional tools. These factors were divided into didactic, psychological, economic and physiological groups. The didactic requirements for pedagogical software tools include: scientific, intelligible, strict and systematic description (allowing the possibility to build the content of educational activities, taking into account the basic principles of pedagogy, psychology, informatics, ergonomics, the fundamental foundations of modern science 'providing'), continuity and integrity (it is a logical consequence and complement of previously learned knowledge), consistency, problem, demonstrability, activation (independence of teaching and the presence of the characteristic of activity), consistency of mastering the results of teaching, interactivity of communication, teaching, education, development and integrated unity of practice.

Currently, the Hemis online information system has been launched in the higher education system. This system provides great convenience to students and teaching professors.

Hemis — Uzbekistan is one of the innovations in the field of education, a platform that meets world standards and supports the use of new methods in personnel training.

The educational process is one of the most important sectors of every country, and its effectiveness determines the future of this country. Teaching informatics in higher education institutions serves to develop the field of information technologies.

It is also possible to organize classes using many educational methods in teaching "Network technologies".

Educational technology - refers to the process of using computer technology, software, and educational theory and practice together to facilitate learning. In addition to practical educational experience, educational technology is based on theoretical knowledge from various disciplines such as communication, education, psychology, sociology, artificial intelligence, and computer science. It covers several areas such as learning theory, computer-based learning, online learning, and m-learning using mobile technologies.

Method – (derived from the Greek word "methodos", which means the way, the method of ethics). The way of knowing and researching the phenomena of nature and social life. Activity, way, method or appearance, form, appearance of movement.

Educational method – a method of work that a teacher regularly uses with students, which allows students to develop their intellectual abilities and interests, acquire knowledge and skills, and use them in practice. It is a set of regulated methods of organizing the mutual activities of the teacher and the students in order to achieve the specified educational goal.

Methodology – a set of methods, ways of carrying out a task in accordance with the purpose. It consists of separate methods. In the field of pedagogy, it researches the laws of teaching and educational work of a certain academic subject. For example, methods of languages, methods of arithmetic, etc.

Method of education – a way of learning or doing something, event, process.

Learning style – a set of methods that should be used to study or implement something, an event, a process.

Method is a Greek word that means research, a way to achieve a goal.

Method – means the way of achieving the goal, the process of activity organized in a certain way. The main content of the methods is a collection of scientific theories in close contact with practice. Voluntary scientific theory essentially has a methodological function. The method serves as a tool for the creation of new scientific theories and laws.

It is possible to increase the efficiency of the lesson by using various methods in teaching "Network technologies". The correct and appropriate use of educational methods depending on the origin of the subject, the use of the method in each subject have a great impact on the productivity of the lesson.

Researches in the field of didactics show that the solution of didactic problems aimed at mastering the studied material is understood as a combination of the teaching work of the pedagogue and the methods of organizing the learning activities of students. Educational methods appear first of all in the mind of the pedagogue in the form of a generalized project of activity in a certain direction.

Method of education – a component or a separate aspect of the educational method, the relationship between methods and ways is interconnected. Method and ways are connected to each other as whole and part. Only a part of the pedagogical or educational task is solved with the help of methods. The same methodological methods may be used in different ways. And on the contrary, the same method can be revealed by different teachers in different ways.

Classification of traditional (according to the source) educational method

Oral	Demonstrative	Practical	Work with the book	Video method
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Story Conversation Explanation Lecture Discussion	Illustration Demonstration	Exercise Practical Laboratory Didactic game	Read Study Plan Summarize	See, Learn, Control
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Classification of educational methods according to the main didactic goals:

Methods of acquiring new knowledge;

Methods of formation of skills and qualifications;

Methods of applying knowledge in practice;

Methods of strengthening and controlling knowledge, skills and qualifications

Binary methods of education

Teaching methods	Learning methods
Informative	Perform (execute)
Explained	Reproductive
Demonstration-practical	Creative-practical
Explanatory-pronoun	Partly exploratory
Exclamation point	Inquisitive

Case study technology

The main purpose of the case: Types and description of modern educational tools.

Training and production tools in education. Prospects for the development of educational tools. Learning the technology of forming a system of educational tools and their collective use.

Expected results of educational activities:

1) To reveal the peculiarities of the types of modern educational tools;

2.) Sequential modeling of development perspectives of educational tools;

3) Study, analysis and classification of the technology of formation of the system of educational tools.

In order to successfully implement this case, students must have the following knowledge, skills and qualifications

The student should know:

Educational tools, educational and production tools, system of educational tools, collective use, natural objects, educational models, dummies, models, publishing technologies, telecommunications, large models, mass media, computer robotics.

The student should have the following skills:

analysis, comparison, generalization, abstraction, design, modeling.

The student should have the following qualifications:

individual and cooperative work, cognitive, heuristic, creative skills.

The main source of this case is a cabinet, with plates, and it is described on the basis of specific assignments. The main object of the case is directed to the study of the types and description of educational tools and their collective use in vocational education. This is an organizational case, and the information is structured based on tasks.

The volume is moderately structured and intended for training. It is aimed at acquiring skills and qualifications on the subject. According to didactic purposes, cases are directed to the

presentation of problems, their solution, analysis, and the development of a new model and the creation and evaluation of the technology of its application to practice. This case can be used in teaching "Network technologies" and other subjects [3].

Solving the recommended case allows to achieve the following results:

1) structure of the classification of network technology science tools, strengthening of computer knowledge;

2) mastering models for the classification of network technologies science tools by solving assignments;

3) to independently master the skill of modeling the classification of network technology science tools.

4) acquisition of problem -solving skills in the field of network technologies.

ORES method

The general scheme of the FSMU method:

O – state your opinion;

R - give a reason justifying your opinion;

E - give an example that confirms your reason;

S - summarize your point.

Table 1

Creating pedagogical software tools in AutoPlay Media Studio
O - With the help of this program, it is possible to create a whole electronic guide on science by combining the programs that demonstrate, teach, control, and for this, basic computer knowledge is enough, that is, it is not necessary to know any programming language.
R - increases student's level of knowledge, facilitates the work of the teacher.
E - partially plays the role of a teacher in the description of a new topic during the lesson. Here the teacher only supervises. A student can learn a given topic at any time with the help of the created software.
S – With the help of the software created with the help of this program, the level of thinking of students increases, communication with the computer is established, knowledge, skills and qualifications increase, and the work of the teacher is facilitated.

Despite comprehensive bans on the use of mobile and network devices in higher education institutions, students continue to actively use their devices, including in groups. We don't know what methods are used in educational institutions to ban mobile devices, how the teacher controls the situation in the group, and how students overcome these bans, but research data shows that almost all students are connected to the Internet, use mobile phones.

On the other hand, it is better to use personal devices to download, store, use, process and retransmit data. All this can be explained by students' motivation for knowledge and involvement in the educational process, because students should become mature pedagogues in the future.

In conclusion, it can be said that by teaching the science of "Network technologies" for the students of "Mathematics and Informatics" in higher educational institutions, the future generation of specialists in the field of information technologies will grow, and they will become mature specialists who can use modern technologies.

It is recommended to use innovative methods and put them into practice in teaching "Network Technologies". Students studying in higher educational institutions should know network technologies, because the effective use of network technologies opens a wide path to the possibilities of using Internet services.

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